

Using Open Educational Resources in Constructing Students' Individual Learning Trajectories

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Open education resources, individual learning trajectory, Humanities and Social Studies majors

Purpose of this paper

The present study is devoted to describing the procedure of constructing individual learning trajectories (ILTs) on the basis of open educational resources (OER) by the Humanities and Social Studies majors in Mariupol State University (Ukraine).

Mariupol State University (MSU), Ukraine, aims to ensure flexible education for its students; therefore the online study portal is designed to provide students and teachers with access to distance learning resources: teaching materials and courses taught in the university. The materials can be used both for organizing students' self-study work and as support for their full-time study. Besides, there is the Electronic Institutional Repository of Mariupol State University (the eIR of MSU) that is included in the *OpenDOAR global directory* of academic open access repositories. The eIR of MSU is intended for accumulation, arrangement and storage in electronic media of the university staff intellectual property: conference and workshop papers, theses and dissertations, books, chapters and sections, etc (The Electronic Institutional Repository of Mariupol State University [the eIR of MSU], n.d.). However, understanding open education philosophy and experience of its implementation is relatively little in MSU and, thus, it still needs to be adopted and promoted in both pre-service and in-service training processes. It is essential in this regard to raise students' awareness of open education opportunities, in particular, using open educational resources (OER), for instance, in designing their own learning trajectories.

A recent review of the literature on this topic shows that scholars mainly consider a broader concept of an *educational trajectory*. In their introduction to *Governance of Educational Trajectories in Europe* M. Cuconato, R. Dale, M. Parreira and A. Walther describe it in a wider sense as institutionally expected *progression* in education and as the subjective *experience* that the individuals make of it (Walther et al., 2016). Other authors state that students' educational trajectories are the *result* of complex interactions between societal institutions and individual-subjective action (Tikkanen, Biggart & Pohl, 2016). In a narrower sense, as applied to the learning process, a *learning trajectory* is seen as a *way* through the constantly expanding maze of knowledge to information transmission, dissemination and acquisition, at individual and collective levels (UNESCO, 2015). L. D. Gitelman and A. P. Isaev consider an individualised learning trajectory as a *process* of self-learning and professional growth (Gitelman & Isaev, 2015). Other authors have a similar understanding of the concept under consideration. M. Tanner and F. Sahlström point out that a learning trajectory reflects a process of establishing relations of cohesion and change between current and previous occasions (Tanner & Sahlström, 2018). Other authors duly note that a learning trajectory not only describes a student's cognitive process, but also what things students can or cannot do, students' reasoning and conceptualization, a cognitive obstacle, and mental processes for progressing to higher levels (Anwar & Rofiki, 2018). Besides, a teacher's role in students' learning trajectories cannot be underestimated, i.e. "teachers formatively assess students over time, attend to student thinking, provide appropriate differentiation, design and modify tasks, choose appropriate learning goals, and relate lesson goals to broader curriculum goals" (Wickstrom & Langrall, 2018). In an attempt to integrate the existing definitions of a trajectory concept and highlighting its processual and resultant states, we define *the individual learning trajectory* (ILT) as a student's strategy for acquiring knowledge, improving relevant skills and fostering motivation. As a result of strategy implementation in the learning process students make their own ways to self-education and self-development by creating new original learning products. The role of the teacher consists of algorithmization of students' individual activity, the selection of criteria for analysis of work, peer review, evaluation, etc. Thus, it is recommended that ILT realization is carried out at certain stages and implies using OER. The latter are defined by the OER Paris Declaration 2012 as any "teaching, learning and research materials in any medium, digital or otherwise, that reside in the public domain or have been released under an open license that permits no-cost access, use, adaptation and redistribution by others with no or limited restrictions. Open licensing is built within the existing framework of intellectual property rights as defined by relevant international conventions and respects the authorship of the work" (UNESCO, 2012).

The purpose of the research is to describe the peculiarities of constructing ILTs by Humanities and Social Sciences Majors and the expected effect of raising students' awareness of open education opportunities, fostering their motivation and developing respective skills to use OER in their individual learning practice as well as academic knowledge acquisition.

Design/methodology/approach

A group of 7 students of various academic majors (Culture Studies, History, Journalism, Law, Philology, Primary Education and Psychology) were involved in the process of ILT constructing. Each participant's individual research was based on OER and suggested understanding the nature of leadership and raising awareness of it as part of students' future professional activity.

Pedagogical modeling as a “method of scientific and pedagogical research, means of creation of pedagogical innovations and pedagogical constructs, technologies and techniques, forms and other pedagogically conditioned structures, determination of functions and pedagogical conditions, trends and constraints, and other constituents of scientific research in modern pedagogy” (Konovalov & Kozyreva, 2017) was used for developing an algorithm of ILT constructing at such stages as *Introduction, Motivation, Planning, Implementation, Presentation, Assessment and Reflection ones*. The experiment lasted for 7 weeks. The implementation of the ILT was based on providing the following pedagogical conditions: fostering students' motivation to use OER and avoid plagiarism in their learning process; expanding students' knowledge about open education alongside with acquiring academic knowledge; developing students' skills on the basis of the acquired knowledge to effectively use OER in their individual research work.

Participatory action research (PAR) which includes inquiring into motivations and assumptions and implies that participants conduct individual experiments and collaboratively reflect on these experiences (Vanasupa et al., 2016), design and reflect on experiments as both researchers and subjects of their own research (Mills et al., 2006) was employed for evaluating and encouraging students' motivation for using OER. In the course of the *Implementation* stage the students-participants met with the teacher-coordinator to share their experience of working on ILT. Such discussions enabled us to make the *SWOT analysis* for each student, thus identifying internal (Strengths, Weaknesses) and external (Opportunities, Threats) factors that promote or impede students' research process based on OER.

Concept testing was used to assess completeness of students’ knowledge, i.e. determine whether the participants understand and identify the key concepts, e.g. Open Education, Open Access, OER, Open Licensing, etc. The degree of knowledge completeness was measured by the formula (1)

$$C_{KC} = \frac{N_1}{N_0} \leq 1, \quad (1)$$

where C_{KC} is the coefficient of knowledge completeness,

N_1 is the number of students who answered all test questions correctly and completely,

N_0 is the number of students who answered test questions.

Method of Expert Evaluation was applied for assessing students’ skills to effectively use OER in their individual research work. In general, the above-mentioned skills reflect students’ ability to find open content for their research, use it and share with their peers. In particular, the skills were divided into five groups according to the 5R activities, i.e. retain, reuse, revise, remix and redistribute. The group of experts consisting of university instructors determined the level of skills development by filling in the Expert Evaluation Form (Fig.1).

EXPERT EVALUATION FORM				
Student's Name _____				
Criterion	Indicators	Grades		
		3 Advanced	2 Intermediate	1 Elementary
Skills to effectively use OER in individual research work	retain – selecting, storing and managing the relevant content; reuse – using the content for carrying out an individual research and presenting the results in class; revise – adjusting and modifying the content (rendering the content into a native language); remix – combining the content with other material to create something new; redistribute – sharing copies of the original content, its revisions or its remixes with others			
Expert _____				

Fig. 1. Expert Evaluation Form Sample.

For analysis, a three-point scale was used. The elementary level indicated that there were no obvious changes; the intermediate level – some changes occurred and student’s skills were partly developed but a student was potentially capable of achieving higher results; the advanced level – student’s skills were developed and he/she maximized his/her results.

The average grade for skills development was defined as the arithmetic mean of each student's individual grade by the formula (2).

$$C_{SD} = \frac{G_1 + G_2 + \dots + G_n}{\Sigma_n} \quad (2)$$

where C_{SD} is the coefficient of skills development,

G_1 is an indicator of the skills development level,

Σ_n is the total number of students.

Findings

The *Introduction* stage of ILT constructing (Week 1) was aimed at actualizing the key concepts of open education and accordingly the respective students' knowledge. A special training session "Introduction to Open Education" was conducted for the participants to develop their understanding of its opportunities and teach them how to search for and identify appropriate open resources. The training session covered the following issues: *What is Open Education and Open Knowledge, OER and Open Licenses*. Then the students were offered to construct their own ILTs on a common topic "Leadership" using OER, in particular, OER Commons, a digital library that provides accessible content for finding relevant materials. First of all the students were shown photos of some famous world leaders and asked to collect information about them in the form of brief encyclopaedic entries. After that the students gave their own examples of famous leaders and told about their achievements and what qualities and abilities the leader has (or had). The activity was followed by the whole class discussion of the following questions: *Do the above-mentioned leaders have any common characteristics? Are leaders born or made?* Also the students explained what resources of OER Commons they used for their micro-research. The trainees were encouraged to continue their research project in their respective fields.

The *Motivation* stage (Week 2) was aimed at further developing students' awareness of open education benefits and its effect on their learning process. For this purpose the idea to set up an open textbook display (Yano, 2017) was used. The participants selected necessary open textbooks and monographs on the topic under consideration and then "advertised" them to their fellow students. Therefore having students engage their peers can be a more effective approach to introduce and demonstrate the quality of OER (Yano, 2017). It contributed to provision of the first pedagogical condition – *fostering students' motivation to use OER and avoid plagiarism in their learning process*. At this stage it was also important to develop trainees' personal attitude to leadership as their future professional activity. The participants defined their professional contexts and brainstormed on how leadership can help them improve these contexts. The trainees filled in the Venn diagram with professional and leadership skills in order to represent similarities and differences between them (Fig. 2).

At the *Planning* stage (Week 3) each student acted as the organizer of his/her own learning process by setting a goal, assuming his/her final learning product and forms of its presentation, making a work plan, selecting means and methods of achieving the goal, creating self-monitoring and self-evaluation system. Thus, at this stage, individual learning programmes were composed by the students for the designated period.

The *Implementation* stage (Weeks 3, 4, 5) was meant for carrying out students' individual learning programmes. The provision of the second pedagogical condition – *expanding students' knowledge about open education alongside with acquiring academic knowledge* – was achieved by students' own contribution into enriching the existing learning material. The trainees synthesized knowledge on leadership from the Humanities and Social Sciences, supplemented the learning material with topics related to leadership; designed microlibraries for conducting dissemination events on leadership issues and preparing reports for science research conferences. OER Commons Library served as a knowledge base for students' research.

Fig.2. The Venn Diagram to Compare Philologist' Professional Qualities of and Leadership Ones.

Ensuring the third condition – *developing students' skills on the basis of the acquired knowledge to effectively use OER in their individual research work* – was due to forming peer groups of mutual support for exchanging knowledge and experience on its acquiring. The students in dyads enacted the "Support partners" role play which implied assisting each other while implementing their individual learning programmes, joint information search, etc. Besides, the students were divided into triads for the "Counselling" technique. The triad members performed the roles of an observer, a consultant and a student who asked for advice. The participants exchanged roles, so that everyone could perform all team roles and learn from the experience.

The consultant helped the student find a necessary solution, and the observer watched counsellor’s actions and made conclusions as to their efficiency.

The *Presentation* stage (Week 6) consisted of demonstration of individual learning products and their collective discussion. After completing the ILTs the students presented their results to a peer group and a group of experts. Each student demonstrated his/her advancement in the chosen field of study. The end product and its presentation depended on the student’s academic major (Table 1).

Table 1. Outputs of Students’ Individual Learning Trajectories

Academic Major (Humanities and Social Sciences)	Output Example
Culture Studies	Designing a guide-book on cultural differences between countries, their attitudes towards leadership and cross-cultural leadership.
Journalism	Writing a documentary script, e.g. “Dangers of Charismatic Leadership. Evil Geniuses in History”.
History	Presenting a lively leader’s story in the form of a conference report based on historical research, transferring the evidence and events of the past to the present context, e.g. “Napoleons of Our Days. Who Are They?”
Law	Making an open statement as an attorney for defence for “A Leader Under Trial” role play.
Philology	Compiling a brief dictionary (monolingual/bilingual, lexical/encyclopaedic, etc.) of terms and concepts of leadership
Primary Education	Writing a brief manual for parents devoted to child’s upbringing as a future leader
Psychology	Writing an article for a scientific journal, e.g. “Leadership Psychotypes”.

The *Assessment and Reflection* stage (Week 7) was the final one. The results of the SWOT analysis helped identify the following *Strengths* that promoted students’ research process based on OER: students’ willingness to use and create OER, and relevant level of digital literacy for

this. Among *Weaknesses* the Humanities and Social Sciences majors admitted the lack of foreign language knowledge since the majority of OER were in English; however, the students are required to do most assignments and coursepapers in their native language. As far as *Opportunities* are concerned, the participants emphasised the following: open and free access to a wide range of learning materials, saving time and money for educational resources. All that increased their academic performance and helped to make the learning process more flexible and creative. As *Threats* the students mentioned low open education awareness on the institutional level, i.e. need for more support from instructors and librarians' side.

The results of the concept testing were satisfactory at the end of the experiment (with the coefficient of knowledge completeness equal to 0,85). The average grade for students' skills development constituted 2,45 points. Alongside with experts' evaluation the students determined their own achievement levels and whether they succeeded in achieving their general and individual goals. Each trainee concluded whether his/her self-assessment coincided with the expert group assessment and planned his/her further individual learning trajectory.

Research limitations/implications

The study presents the findings from a particular university and a small number of students involved in the research project. A broader academic environment is needed to measure effectiveness of the designed methodology.

Practical implications

The obtained results will enable to adapt the designed methodology to the needs of students of other academic majors and sufficiently deal with the problem of plagiarism. Besides, the research revealed the necessity to engage a wider audience including librarians and teaching staff into using and creating OER as well as the need for reconsideration and modernization of the existing university strategy of foreign language teaching, in particular English for Specific and Academic Purposes, in order to help students more efficiently access the OER.

What is original/value of paper

The phased implementation of the individual learning trajectory as a student's strategy for acquiring knowledge, improving relevant skills and fostering motivation has been presented in the paper. It has been described how ensuring a complex of respective pedagogical conditions

was possible due to a variety of activities for the participants at each stage of ILT constructing using OER.

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